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Modelling and Forecasting Volatility of Returns on the Nairobi Stock Market using Arch Models

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ABSTRACT

This study empirically models and forecasts volatility (conditional variance) on the Nairobi Stock Market using the ARCH models namely; GARCH-M (1,1), EGARCH-M (1,1) and TGARCH-M (1,1). The daily NSE 20-share index data over a period of 10-years was used in the analysis. The competing volatility models were estimated and their specification and forecast performance compared using RMSE, MAE, MAPE, TIC and R^2 . The NSE stock returns exhibits volatility clustering, asymmetric effects, leptokurtosis which are common characteristics for most financial time series data. Overall, the EGARCH-M (1,1) emerged the best model with the t-distribution over the GARCH-M (1,1) and TGARCH-M (1,1) due to its lower values of the RMSE, MAE and MAPE. Comparison using the R^2 also gave the same results in that the EGARCH-M (1,1) emerged the best due to its highest value of R^2 (0.187010) unlike the TGARCH-M and GARCH-M.

JEL Classification: C22, C53, E17

Keywords

Nairobi Stock Exchange, ARCH models, Volatility, Forecasting.

1. Introduction

Strong and stable financial markets with the possibility to forecast their course indicates growing economist, financial analysts, and policy makers on the macro economy and thus on economic policy in general. Efficient markets are a necessary prerequisite for a growing financial stock market. A stock market is termed to be efficient if it fully reflects all information in the market. An efficient financial market is one in which prices always fully reflect all the available information. Market efficiency is categorized into three forms as weak, semi-strong and strong (Fama 1970, 1991). A study by Muhanji (2000) and Dickson and Muragu (1994) found that NSE had a weak form of efficiency. The EGARCH model applied to the Kenyan and Nigerian Stock Market returns by Ogum *et al.* (2005), established that both the stock markets had a weak form of efficiency.

Modelling volatility in financial markets is important because it sheds further light on the data generating process of the returns. Volatility is a tendency of the assets prices fluctuating either up or down. Increased volatility is perceived as indicating a rise in financial risk which can adversely affect investor assets and wealth. It is observed that when a stock market exhibit increased volatility there is a tendency on the part of investors to lose confidence in the market and they tend to exit the market. Stock return-volatility has received great attention from both academicians and practitioners because it can be used as a measure of risk in financial markets. Studies carried out in the African stock markets include, Frimpong and Oteng (2006) who applied GARCH models to the Ghana Stock Exchange, Suliman *et al.* (2012), applied GARCH models to the Sudan (KSE) and Egypt Stock Exchange (CASE) by modeling Stock Market Volatility while Brooks *et al.* (1997) examined the effect of political change in the South African Stock market.

There is a large literature on modeling and forecasting volatility on emerging stock markets, however, none of such studies has appeared in the literature focusing on the Nairobi Stock Market. Studying African markets integration Piesse and Hearn, (2002), suggested that the univariate EGARCH model by Nelson (1991) are appropriate for the analysis of African market. This is because they successfully model asymmetric impacts of good news (positive shocks) and bad news (negative shocks) on volatility transmission with high levels of accuracy. Using weekly market data from January 1993 to 2000 for Ghana, they found no evidence of asymmetry (leverage effect). This study mainly focuses on modeling and forecasting the conditional variance at NSE market using the ARCH models.

2. The ARCH Models

Autoregressive conditional heteroscedasticity (ARCH) model, introduced by Engle (1982) modelled the United Kingdom inflation by allowing the variance of the error term to vary over-time. ARCH models are capable of modelling and capturing many of the stylized facts of the volatility behavior usually observed in financial time series including time varying volatility or volatility clustering (Zivot and Wang, 2005). This model allows the conditional variance to change over time as a function of past errors leaving the unconditional variance constant. Engle (1982).

2.1 The GARCH model

To avoid the long lag of the ARCH (q) developed by Engle (1982), Bollerslev (1986), generalized the ARCH model, called the (GARCH), by including the lagged values of the conditional variance. GARCH model is one of the widely used ARCH-type model (Engle, 2004). Bollerslev (1986) proposed an extension of the conditional variance function which he termed as the generalized ARCH (GARCH) and suggested that conditional variance be specified as,

$$h_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \varepsilon_{t-1}^2 + \dots + \alpha_q \varepsilon_{t-q}^2 + \beta_1 h_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_p h_{t-p} \quad (1)$$

with the inequality condition $\alpha_0 > 0, \alpha_i \geq 0$ for $i=1, \dots, q$, $\beta_i \geq 0$ for $i=1, \dots, p$ to ensure that conditional variance is strictly positive. The simplest GARCH (1,1) is often found to be the most efficient in modeling time series Stock market data since GARCH (p, q) model, where $(p + q > 2)$, leads to increased estimation of risk when considering potential regime in the model.

In contrast to the empirical success, GARCH models have one major disadvantage; they are unable to model asymmetric effect or leverage effect due to the positive and negative shocks of the same magnitude resulting to the same amount of volatility.

A special case of the GARCH (p, q) models, the simple GARCH (1,1) model is given as,

$$\sigma_t^2 = \omega + \alpha_1 \varepsilon_{t-1}^2 + \beta_1 \sigma_{t-1}^2 + \beta_2 \sigma_{t-2}^2 \tag{2}$$

where

$$\omega > 0, \alpha_1 \geq 0, \beta_1 \geq 0.$$

As seen from (1), the model is constructed with non-negative constraints for all alphas and betas. The parameters α_1 and β_1 determine the short-run dynamics of the resulting volatility time series. A large value of the GARCH lag coefficient β_1 indicates that shocks to conditional variance will take long time to die out. In other words it means the volatility is persistent. A large value of α_1 implies that the volatility will react quite intensely to movements in the market. If $\alpha_1 + \beta_1$ is close to unity a shock at time t will persist for many periods in the future. A high sum value of $(\alpha_1 + \beta_1)$ therefore implies persistence. If $\alpha_1 + \beta_1 = 1$, it implies that a shock will lead to a permanent change in all future values of σ_t .

2.2 The EGARCH model

The EGARCH model of Nelson (1991) is the first asymmetric GARCH model. This model looks at the conditional variance and tries to accommodate for the asymmetric relation between stock returns and volatility changes. The EGARCH model is also used to test the hypothesis that the variance of return was influenced differently by positive and negative excess returns. The model captures the leverage effect in the financial market that the main GARCH model is not able. The specification for the higher order conditional variance for the EGARCH model is given as,

$$\text{Log}(\sigma_t^2) = \omega_0 + \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j \log(\sigma_{t-j}^2) + \left(\sum_i^q \alpha_i \left| \frac{\varepsilon_{t-i}}{\sigma_{t-i}} \right| + \gamma_i \frac{\varepsilon_{t-i}}{\sigma_{t-i}} \right) \tag{3}$$

where $\varepsilon_t = \eta_t \sqrt{\sigma_t}$ as $\eta_t \sim \text{i.i.d N}(0,1)$.

The parameter (α_i) in equation (3) measures the impact of innovation at time t while parameter (β_j) is the auto-regressive term on lagged conditional volatility, reflecting the weight given to previous period's conditional volatility t .

A special case of EGARCH (p,q) models, the EGARCH (1,1) model is given as,

$$\text{Log}(\sigma_t^2) = \omega_1 + \beta_1 \log(\sigma_{t-1}^2) + \alpha_1 \left[\frac{|\varepsilon_{t-1}|}{\sigma_{t-1}} - E \left\{ \frac{\varepsilon_{t-1}}{\sigma_{t-1}} \right\} \right] + \gamma_1 \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{t-1}}{\sigma_{t-1}} \right) \quad (4)$$

where,

$$E \left(\frac{|\varepsilon_{t-1}|}{\sigma_{t-1}} \right) = E \{ |Z_{t-1}| \} = \sqrt{2/\pi}$$

with degrees of freedom $\nu > 2$.

The left-hand side of equation (4) is the log of the conditional variance, which implies that the asymmetric effect is exponential, rather than quadratic, and that forecasts of the conditional variance are generated to be non-negative. The presence of leverage effect can be tested by the hypothesis that $\gamma < 0$. The impact is asymmetric if $\gamma \neq 0$.

EGARCH model has several advantages compared to the GARCH model. In the EGARCH model σ_t^2 is logged which means that although the parameters are negative, σ_t^2 will be positive. This implies that the model needs no assumption of non-negative constraints as for the GARCH model. But a necessary assumption for the EGARCH model is the assumption of stationarity in the time series. The EGARCH model allows for asymmetries, which is defined as the parameter estimate γ . If the leverage term is negative, it implies a negative relationship between volatility and returns. In the EGARCH model the persistence is entirely captured by the β_1 term.

2.3 The TGARCH model

The Threshold GARCH (TGARCH) model developed by [Zakoian \(1994\)](#) is similar to GJR ARCH, and the specification is one on conditional standard deviation instead of conditional variance.

$$h_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{j=1}^q \beta_j h_{t-j} + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_i \varepsilon_{t-i}^2 + \sum_{k=1}^r \gamma_k \varepsilon_{t-k}^2 I_{t-k}^- \quad (5)$$

where $\varepsilon_t = \eta_t \sqrt{h_t}$ and $I_t^- = 1$, if $\varepsilon_t < 0$ and zero otherwise. In the TGARCH model, $\varepsilon_{t-i} > 0$ indicates positive shocks (good news), and $\varepsilon_{t-i} < 0$ bad news, this has differential effect on the conditional variance. Good news has an impact of α_i , while bad news has an impact of $\alpha_i + \gamma_i$. If $\gamma_i > 0$, bad news increases volatility while if $\gamma_i \neq 0$, the news impact is asymmetric.

A special case of TGARCH (p, q) model, the TGARCH (1,1) is given by;

$$h_t = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 h_{t-1} + \alpha_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} + \gamma_1 \varepsilon_{t-1}^2 I_{t-1}^- \quad (6)$$

where I_t takes value 1 for $\varepsilon_t < 0$, and 0 otherwise. So ‘good news’ (positive shocks) and ‘bad news’ (negative shocks) have a different impact. Good news has an impact parameter estimate γ , while bad news has an impact of $\gamma + \theta$. If $\theta > 0$ there is asymmetry, while if $\theta = 0$ the news impact is symmetric. When the threshold term I_{t-k}^- is set to zero, then equation (6) becomes a GARCH (p,q) model.

3. METHODOLOGY AND DATA

3.1 Determination of Forecast Performance

Literature based on forecast performance in Africa, show that ordinary GARCH models are successful in estimating and forecasting volatility to simpler parsimonious models. The GARCH, EGARCH and TGARCH models were estimated for forecast performance of the NSE 20-share index returns series using the robust method of [Bollerslev and Wooldridge \(1992\)](#), the Quasi-Maximum Likelihood Estimator (QMLE) assuming the Gaussian standard normal distribution. The QMLE (or composite likelihood estimate) is an estimate of the parameter θ in a statistical model that is formed by maximizing a function that is related to the logarithm of the likelihood function. This technique adjusts for small deviations from normality. The Akaike Information Criteria and Maximum Log-Likelihood (ML) values and a set of model diagnostic tests (ARCH-LM test, and Q-statistics tests) were used to choose the model that describes the conditional variance of the NSE 20-share index. Common measures of forecast evaluation, the Random Mean Squared Error (RMSE), the Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) and the Theil Inequality Coefficient (TIC) were used to show the performance of each model. The model that exhibited the lowest values of error measurements was considered the best.

The MAPE was used to measure accuracy in the fitted time series models the GARCH, EGARCH and TGARCH given as,

$$M = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \left| \frac{A_t - F_t}{A_t} \right| \quad (7)$$

where, A_t was the actual value and F_t the forecast value.

The MAE and RMSE were used to measure the average magnitude of the errors in a set of forecast for each of the three time series models. If RMSE calculated value is equal to MSE value, then all the errors are of the same magnitude. RMSE was given as,

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \left(\hat{\sigma}_t^2 - \sigma_t^2 \right)^2} \quad (8)$$

where, n is the sample size and σ_t^2 conditional variance.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Forecasting

The models were also evaluated in terms of their forecasting ability of future returns. The common measure of forecast evaluation the RMSE, MAE, MAPE and TIC were used. In Table 1 the results of the in-sample forecast performance are shown. The model that exhibits the lowest values of the error measurements was considered to be the best. The results clearly indicated the asymmetric EGARCH-M (1,1) model outperformed all the other models. The symmetric GARCH-M (1,1) performed the least in forecasting the conditional volatility of the NSE 20-Share index returns. These results contradict the findings of Dimson and Marsh (1990) that relatively complex nonlinear models are inferior in forecasting to simpler parsimonious models. The Bias Proportion showed how far the mean of forecast is from the mean of the actual series while the covariance proportion measured the remaining unsystematic forecasting errors of the actual series. The large variance proportion (0.9998315) indicated that the forecast tracked the seasonal (movements) variation in the NSE returns only at the beginning of the forecast sample and quickly flatten out to the mean forecast value. Figure 1 and 2 presents the in-sample and out-of-sample volatility forecast and variance forecast of the NSE returns.

Table 1: Dynamic Forecast Performance Estimated Models (In-Sample)

	GARCH-M (1,1)	EGARCH-M(1,1)	TGARCH-M (1,1)
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.011935	0.011935	0.011935
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.006443	0.006438	0.006442
Mean Abs. Percent Error (MAPE)	121.4006	112.7396	119.8458
Theil Inequality Coefficient (TIC)	0.969317	0.978756	0.970912
Overall Rank	3	1	2
Bias Proportion	0.000009	0.000047	0.000002
Variance Proportion	0.998132	0.9998315	0.998176
Covariance Proportion	0.001859	0.000638	0.001822
R ²	0.191638	-0.020676	0.150072

Table 2 shows the results of out-of-sample forecast performance. The asymmetric TGARCH-M (1,1) model exhibits the lowest values of the error measurements thus was considered the best choice with normal distribution. This is supported by its lowest R^2 value (-0.017704) compared to the others. The R-Squared (R^2) statistics measures the success of the regression in predicting the values of the dependent variable within the sample. It can be negative if the regression does not have an intercept or constant, if the regression contains coefficient restrictions, or if the estimation method is two-stage least squares or ARCH- type model. The asymmetric EGARCH-M performed the least unlike in the dynamic forecast where it performed the best. These findings also contradict the results of Dimson and Marsh (1990). The in-sample results display both leptokurtosis and asymmetric effect. Out-of-sample forecasts depict the asymmetric effects.

Table 2: Static Forecast Performance of Estimated Models (In-Sample)

	GARCH-M (1,1)	EGARCH-M(1,1)	TGARCH-M (1,1)
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.011869	0.011800	0.11866
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.006436	0.006437	0.006435
Mean Abs. Percent Error (MAPE)	104.4194	105.7880	102.1423
Theil Inequality Coefficient (TIC)	0.937924	0.924375	0.931663
Overall Rank	2	3	1
Bias Proportion	0.000830	0.001047	0.000487
Variance Proportion	0.893793	0.886462	0.881719
Covariance Proportion	0.105377	0.112491	0.117795
R^2	-0.017544	-0.010423	-0.017704

Figure 1: Dynamic Volatility Forecast and Forecast of Variance Graphs

Figure 2: Static Volatility Forecast and Forecast of Variance Graphs

5. CONCLUSION

The volatility of the NSE returns have been modeled for forecasting using non-linear symmetric GARCH-M(1,1) and the asymmetric EGARCH-M (1,1) and TGARCH-M (1,1) models. NSE 20-share index was found to exhibit volatility clustering, leptokurtosis and asymmetric effects which is associated with many stock markets. Considering forecast performance, the asymmetric EGARCH-M (1,1) with dynamic forecast model emerged the best with student's t-distribution over the GARCH-M and TGARCH-M due to its lower values in RMSE, MAE and MAPE. Comparison using the R^2 also gave the same results in that the EGARCH-M (1,1) emerged the best due to its highest value of R^2 (0.184244) unlike the TGARCH-M and GARCH-M. Therefore, in forecasting the NSE market future returns, the asymmetric models EGARCH-M (1,1) and TGARCH-M (1,1) with student's t-distribution and normal distribution respectively are recommended.

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